

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Metal	N	
1.	[UO ₂ (DAN-Benz)(NO ₃) ₂]	32.41 (32.69)	7.61 (7.69)	35
2.	[UO ₂ (DAN-Sal)]	34.33 (37.53)	6.10 (4.41)	52
3.	[UO ₂ (DAN-Van)]	32.89 (34.29)	5.83 (4.03)	51
4.	[Th(DAN-Benz)(NO ₃) ₂]	28.25 (28.50)	9.97 (10.31)	55
5.	[Th(DAN-Sal)(NO ₃) ₂]	29.61 (32.22)	9.17 (7.77)	53
6.	[Th(DAN-Van)(NO ₃) ₂]	27.93 (29.74)	8.18 (7.17)	51

respectively. The free nitrate bands appearing at 1035–970 cm^{-1} was split into two bands, 1530–1480 and 1290–1250 cm^{-1} on coordination¹⁰. It was difficult to assign the 1530–1480 cm^{-1} band in the complexes as this was the region of C=C frequency also. The band appearing in the region 1260–1240 cm^{-1} in complexes of Sl. nos. 1, 4, 5 and 6 was assigned to coordinated nitrate group. The band found in the region 510–530 cm^{-1} in complexes of Sl. nos. 1–3 is ascribed to $\nu_{\text{U-N}}$ and the band at 545–450 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{Th-N}}$ in complexes of Sl. nos. 4–6 (Table 1)¹¹. The 440–460 cm^{-1} band in the complexes of Sl. nos. 2, 3, 5 and 6 was assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ modes¹².

The electronic spectra of as the complexes in solution showed no distinct bands in the region 330–750 nm. The typical electronic spectral band expected due to the UO₂^{II} group at 390–450 nm in the complexes were masked by the strong charge transfer and ligand absorption bands appearing in this region.

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Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of some Trivalent Lanthanides with Salicylidene Anthranilic Acid†

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SOME of the thermodynamic properties of lanthanides have revealed that they may be placed into two groups with Gd^{III} as the dividing species¹. In the present communication, an attempt is made to establish the relationship between some rare earth metal ions belonging to the first half of the lanthanide series, i.e. Pr^{III}(f²), Nd^{III}(f³), Sm^{III}(f⁵) and Gd^{III}(f⁷). With this view we have undertaken the potentiometric studies of complex formation of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} with salicylidene anthranilic acid (SAAA) in 50% (v/v) ethanol–water medium at two temperatures 32 and 42 ± 1° and at an approximately constant ionic strength (μ) of 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were either of A.R. grade or purified before use. The ligand was prepared by following the procedure as described earlier². The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1 M perchloric acid solution and standardised by EDTA method³.

pH-metric titration method of Bjerrum–Calvin^{4,5} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶ was followed to determine the formation constant values. The experimental procedure is the same as mentioned

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earlier⁷. Duplicate titrations were performed and the results obtained were identical in each case. Correction for pH measurements in aquo-organic solvent system has been made as described by Van Uitert and Hass⁸. The proton-ligand formation constants ($\log K_n^H$) were evaluated by following standard methods⁸. From the pH-titration curve (Fig. 1), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated and the complexation equilibrium constants were obtained as usual⁸. The following solutions were titrated against 0.5 M NaOH having total volume of 50 ml in 50% (v/v) ethanol water medium: acid, 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄+5 ml 1 M NaClO₄+10 ml water+25 ml ethanol; ligand, 10 ml 0.1 M HClO₄+5 ml 1 M NaClO₄+4×10⁻³ M ligand+10 ml water+25 ml ethanol; metal, 5 ml 0.1 M HClO₄+5 ml 1 M NaClO₄+4×10⁻³ M ligand+5 ml 0.01 M metal salt solution+10 ml water+25 ml ethanol (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. pH-titration curve at 32° and $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄): (A) acid curve, (L) ligand curve; and metal curve: (x) Pr, (▲) Nd, (●) Sm, (○) Gd.

Results and Discussion

Formation of polynuclear species was unimportant at the very low concentration of the metal ions used. The metal-ligand complexation occurred at pH much lower than that of hydrolysis of the metal ions^{9,10} and hydroxo species were therefore neglected. $\bar{n}$, pL plots consisted of distinct portions $0 < \bar{n} < 1$ and $1 < \bar{n} < 2$ which clearly indicated the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes in stepwise manner. The metal-ligand formation constants, evaluated by different computational methods⁸, are shown in Table 1. It is observed that the stability constants show an increasing trend as the tempera-

ture decreases suggesting thereby that low temperature is favourable for complexation. The overall stoichiometric stability constants were found to be in the order, Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} > Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND* STABILITY CONSTANTS WITH SALICYLIDENE ANTHRANILATE (SAAA)

Temp = 32° (42°), Ethanol - Water = 50% (v/v), $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

	H ⁺	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	Gd ^{III}
$\log K_1^H$	8.39 (8.16)	—	—	—	—
$\log K_2^H$	5.54 (5.34)	—	—	—	—
$\log K_1$	—	9.08 (8.12)	9.51 (9.71)	8.67 (7.87)	8.32 (7.41)
$\log K_2$	—	4.99 (4.47)	5.23 (4.78)	4.78 (4.62)	4.64 (4.31)

* At 32° and that in parenthesis at 42°.

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Study of N-(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxylamine, N-(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-3,4-dimethylaniline and N-(2,4-Dihydroxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine as Metal Chelates and as Chemotherapeutic Agents

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POTENTIOMETRIC studies have been carried out on metal chelates of UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with N-(2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene)hydroxyl-